

TOWARDS EMOTION BASED SONG RECOMMENDATION SYSTEM

Prachi Gupta¹, Divya¹, Nikita Sharma¹, Rahul Deva²

¹Student, Department of CSE, JEMTEC, Greater Noida

²Assistant Professor, Department of CSE, JEMTEC, Greater Noida

¹rajeshgupta91704@gmail.com, ¹divyakarn0511@gmail.com, ¹snitika743@gmail.com

Abstract— the required input is extracted from the human face directly using a camera and one of the applications of this input can be for extracting the information to deduce the mood of an individual. this data can then be used to get a list of songs that comply with the “mood” derived from the input provided earlier. this eliminates the time consuming and tedious task of manually segregating or grouping songs helps in generating an appropriate playlist based on an individual's emotional features facial expression based music player aims at scanning and interpreting the data and accordingly creating a playlist based the parameters provided thus our proposed system focus on detecting human emotions for developing emotion based music player, which are the approaches used by available music players to detect emotions . It is a tedious job to select a song as there are thousands of songs in a playlist, consequently users face the problem of selecting songs manually and through the playlist based on their current mood, thus Emotion based music player is being implemented. Human emotion detection is in need of demand, the modern artificial intelligent systems can emulate and gauge reactions from face. Machine learning algorithms are suitable for detection and predictions of emotions. A camera captures user's image, detects the person's expression and maps the mood and plays music according to the playlist accomplished. Emotion Based Music Player helps the user by sensing their emotion, plays the song, also recommends related songs that would comfort or resonates to the user's state of mind. An image of the user is captured by the system. The music playlist will be displayed and songs will be played to boost the user's mood after successful detection of the face.

Key Words: Emotion Recognition, Linear classifier, Facial Landmark Extraction, SVM Classification

1. INTRODUCTION

Music plays an important role in human beings life. It is proven that listening to music helps in reducing stress and produces dopamine (hormone) which regulates in good/relaxed mood. Music player is an application for playing digital audio files and allow users to organize their multimedia collection, play songs. Artificial intelligence (AI) is a technology that enables a machine to simulate human behaviour. Machine learning is a subset of Artificial Intelligence which allows a machine to automatically learn from past data without programming explicitly. The goal of Artificial Intelligence is to make smart computer to solve complex problems, Emotion based music player uses Artificial intelligence and Machine Learning to make decisions and recognize the emotions regarding identification of Facial expressions. It is a tedious job to select a song as there are thousands of songs in a playlist, consequently users face the problem of selecting songs manually through the playlist based on their current mood, thus Emotion based music player is being implemented.

Human emotion detection is in need of demand, the modern artificial intelligent systems can emulate and gauge reactions from face. Machine learning algorithms are suitable for detection and predictions A camera captures user's image, detects the person's expression, maps the mood and plays music according to the playlist accomplished. Emotion Based Music Player helps the user by sensing their emotion, plays the song, also recommends related songs that would comfort or

resonates to the user's state of mind. An image of the user is captured by the system. The image gets analyzed by software and will be classified into happy, sad, neutral, angry emotion. The data gets extracted and detected with the training datasets. The music playlist will be displayed and songs will be played to boost the user's mood after successful detection of the face. When using conventional music players, the user had to manually browse the playlist and choose songs that would lift his or her spirits and emotional state. The work required a lot of labour, and coming up with a suitable list of tunes was frequently difficult. The development of Music Information Retrieval (MIR) and Audio Emotion Recognition (AER) provided the traditional systems with a function that automatically parsed the playlist based on various emotional classifications. The goal of Audio Emotion Recognition (AER) is to classify audio signals according to distinct emotional categories using certain audio properties. An important aspect of the study of music information recognition (MIR) is the extraction of distinct audio aspects from an audio stream. By eliminating the need for manual playlist segmentation and song annotation based on user emotion, AER and MIR improved the functionality of conventional music players. However, these systems lacked the necessary mechanisms to allow a music player to be controlled by a user's emotions. Information retrieval methods are less efficient since the current algorithms produce unpredictable returns and frequently increase the system's overall memory overheads. They are unable to quickly extract useful information from an auditory source. Current audio emotion recognition algorithms use mood models that are slackly connected to a user's perception. The state-of-the art lacks designs that can create a personalised playlist by deducing human emotions from a facial image without using additional resources. The current designs either use extra hardware or human voice. The project suggests an approach designed to reduce the downsides and flaws of the current technology. The project's main goal is to create a precise algorithm that will produce a playlist of songs from a user's playlist in accordance with that user's emotional state. The algorithm is less computationally intensive, uses less storage, and costs less to use

more hardware. It classifies face images into one of four categories: sad, angry, neutral, or happy.

2. LITERATURE WORK

Anagha S. Dhavalikar et al [1] proposed Automatic Facial Expression recognition system. In This system there are three phase i.e, Face detection, Feature Extraction and Expression recognition. The First Phase Face Detection are done by RGB colour model, and lighting compensation for getting face and morphological operations for retaining required face and eyes and mouth of the face. This System is also used AAM, Active Appearance Model Method for facial feature extraction In this method the point on the face like eye, eyebrows and mouth are located and it create a data file which gives information about model points detected and detect the face the an expression are given as input AAM Model changes according to expression. Yong-Hwan Lee, Woori Han and Youngseop Kim proposed system based on Bezier curve fitting [2]. This system used two step for facial expression and emotion first one is detection and analysis of facial area from input original image and next phase is verification of facial emotion of characteristics feature in the region of interest. The first phase for face detection it uses colour still image based on skin colour pixel by initialized spatial filtering ,based on result of lighting compassion then to estimate face position and facial location of eye and mouth it used feature map After extracting region of interest this system extract points of the feature map to apply Bezier curve on eye and mouth The for understanding of emotion this system uses training and measuring the difference of Hausdorff distance With Bezier curve between entered face image and image from database. Arto Lehtiniemi and Jukka Holm et al [3] proposed system on animated mood picture in music recommendation. On this system the user interact with a collection of images to receive music recommendation with respect to genre of picture. This music recommendation system is developed by Nokia researched center. This system uses textual meta tags for describing the genre and audio signal processing . F. Abdat, C. Maaoui et al and A. Pruski et al. They proposed an system fully automatic facial expression and recognition system based on three step face detection, facial

characteristics extraction and facial expression classification [4]. This system proposed anthropometric model to detect the face feature point combined to Shi and Thomasi method. In this method the variation of 21 distances which describe the facial feature from neutral face and the classification base on SVM (Support Vector Machine). Fang-Fei Kuo et al and Suh-Yin Lee et al.[5] With the growth of digital music, the development of music recommendation is helpful for users. The existing recommendation approaches are based on the users' preference on music. However, sometimes, recommending music according to the emotion is needed. In this paper, we propose a novel model for emotion-based music recommendation, which is based on the association discovery from film music. We investigated the music feature extraction and modified the affinity graph for association discovery between emotions and music features. Experimental result shows that the proposed approach achieves 85% accuracy in average. Ivana Andjelkovic et al and John O'Donovan et al [6] they proposed that a large body of research in recommender systems focuses on optimizing prediction and ranking. However, recent work has highlighted the importance of other aspects of the recommendations, including transparency, control and user experience in general. Building on these aspects, we introduce Mood Play, a hybrid recommender system music which integrates content and mood-based filtering in an interactive interface. We show how Mood Play allows the user to explore a music collection by latent affective dimensions, and we explain how to integrate user input at recommendation time with predictions based on a preexisting user profile. Results of a user study (N=240) are discussed, with four conditions being evaluated with varying degrees of visualization, interaction and control. Anukriti Dureha et al [7]. In this he proposed Manual segregation of a playlist and annotation of songs, in accordance with the current emotional state of a user, is labour intensive and time consuming. Numerous algorithms have been proposed to automate this process. However the existing algorithms are slow, increase the overall cost of the system by using additional hardware (e.g. EEG systems and sensors) and have less accuracy. This paper presents an algorithm that

automates the process of generating an audio playlist, based on the facial expressions of a user, for rendering salvage of time and labor, invested in performing the process manually. The algorithm proposed in this paper aspires to reduce the overall computational time and the cost of the designed system. It also aims at increasing the accuracy of the designed system. The facial expression recognition module of the proposed algorithm is validated by testing the system against user dependent and user independent dataset. Bruce Ferwerda et al and Markus Schedl et al [8] proposed that the initial research assumptions to improve music recommendations by including personality and emotional states. By including these psychological factors, we believe that the accuracy of the recommendation can be enhanced. The system gives attention to how people use music to regulate their emotional states, and how this regulation is related to their personality.

3. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The human face plays an important role in knowing an individual's mood. Camera is used to get the required input from the human face. One of the applications of this input can be for extracting the information to deduce the mood of an individual. The "emotion" derived from the input provided earlier are used to get a list of songs. This tedious task of manually Segregating or grouping songs into different lists are reduced and helps in generating an appropriate playlist based on an individual's emotional features[9]. Facial Expression Based Music Player aims at scanning and interpreting the data and accordingly creating a playlist based the parameters provided. Thus our proposed system focus on detecting human emotions for developing emotion based music player, which are the approaches used by available music players to detect emotions, which approach our music player follows to detect human emotions and how it is better to use our system for emotion detection[10]. A brief idea about our systems working, playlist generation and emotion classification is also given. In this project, we used psycharm tool for analysis. The outcome of the project is split into 2 phases: 1. Develop a software to recognize user emotion based on facial expression using Python. 2. Integrate the python

code into the web service and play the music based on the facial expression.

4. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The face of the person is recorded in the web cam. The recorded video is converted in to frames[11]. Using Pre processing the facial expression are converted in to a sequence of Action Units (AUs) from the image obtained from the webcam. The Facial Action Coding (FACS) is a system that describes all the facial expressions using combinations of the 64 AUs. After Feature Extraction, the Emotions are classified whether it is Happy, Angry, Sad and Surprise faces. The webservices are integrated with them[12]. They may be of SAAS, IAAS, PAAS. The emotions are transferred and the music are played from the emotions detected.

Figure No.1 Overall Architecture Diagram of the Emotion Based Music Recommendation System

5. METHODOLOGY

The main objective of face detection technique is to identify the face in the frame by reducing the external noises and other factors. The steps involved in the FACE DETECTION PROCESS

are image pyramid, histogram of oriented gradients and linear classifier . The data that are obtained are decomposed into the sampling image using image pyramid into multiple scales. The use of this technique is simply to extract features while reducing the noise and the other factors[13]. The low pass image pyramid technique (also known as Gaussian pyramid) consists of smoothing the frame and subsampling it by decreasing its resolution, the process needs to be repeated a few times in order to obtain a perfect result that in the end of the process we obtain a frame similar to the original one but with a decreased resolution and an increased smoothing level[14]. Flow diagram of the module – Face Detection Commonly used to detect objects in images in the field of image processing, HOG Commonly used to detect objects in images in the field of image processing, HOG is a feature descriptor, a technique that counts occurrences of gradient orientation in a localized portion of an image. The main objective of using this technique is to describe the face within the image with a set of distributions of intensity gradients. The linear classification step is the last step in the face detection process. We simply used the linear classifier instead of the SVM to decrease the computational time that the classification process will take and so to guarantee a faster face detection operation. When the face is successfully detected, a bounding box will be applied as an overlay on the image to extract the ROI (face) for further analysis. The extracted ROI will next be processed using the “Predictor” function which is also a called script to extract the 68 facial landmark points and save them in an array[15]. Next, the data stored in the features array will be put in as an input into a PCA reduction code that will reduce the size of data and eliminate any correlated coordinates leaving only the necessary points as principal components. The data is a 68x2 array; 68 points, each point with coordinates on x-axes and y-axes. The array will be converted into a vector containing 136 row and 1 column. The facial landmark extraction code “Predictor” is trained with a set of images and landmark maps for each image. Flow diagram of the module – Emotion Classification The code learns how to extract the facial landmark map of a given face image based on the pixel’s intensity values indexed of each point using regression trees

trained with gradient boosting algorithm. After the PCA reduction operation, the obtained data will be used for classification. A multiclass SVM with a linear kernel is employed to compare the inputted data with stored one to see in what class (emotion) it belongs[16]. If one of the three emotions anger, fear, or surprise is detected a speed decreasing command will be executed to reduce the speed of the wheelchair to prevent the user from endangerment. The input is acquired in real-time so the camera is used to capture the video and then the framing are done. The hidden markov model classification are used for processing the framed images. The frames that are obtained are considered in all frames and all pixel formats for the purpose of emotion classification . The value of each landmark in the face is calculated and is stored for future use. The efficiency of classifier is about 90-95%[17]. so that even when there is any changes in the face due to environmental conditions the system can still identify the face and the emotion being expressed .The emotions are then identified using the values that are obtained that are being set and from the value of the pixel that is received is being compared to that of the values that is present as threshold in the code. The values is transferred to the web service. The song are played from the emotion detected. The emotions are assigned for every song. When the emotion is transferred the respective song will be plays[18]. There are four emotions that can be used and the emotions are happy, anger, sad, surprise. When the happy emotion is recognized the songs that are assigned for that particular emotion are played and the same happens with the other emotions as well that is it the songs are played for the emotions detected respectively.

Figure No.2 Flow diagram of the module – Emotion Classification

6. RESULT

The input is acquired in real-time so the camera is used to capture the video and then the framing are done. The model classification are used for processing the framed images. The frames that are obtained and considered in all frames and all pixel formats for the purpose of emotion classification . The value of each landmark in the face is calculated and is stored for future use. The efficiency of classifier is about 90-95%. so that even when there is any changes in the face due to environmental conditions the system can still identify the face and the emotion being expressed .The emotions are then identified using the values that are obtained that are being set and from the value of the pixel that is received is being compared to that of the values that is present as threshold in the code. The values is transferred to the web service. The song are played from the emotion detected. The emotions are assigned for every song. When the emotion is transferred the respective song will be plays. There are four emotions that can be used and the emotions are happy, anger, sad, surprise. When the happy emotion is recognized the songs that are assigned for that particular emotion are played and the same happens with the other emotions as well that is it the songs are played for the emotions detected respectively.

Figure 3: Different Types of Emotions

7. FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

The music player based on facial recognition system is highly essential for all the person in modern day life ecology. This system is further enhanced with benefit able features for upgrading in future. The methodology of enhancement in the automatic play of songs are done by detection of the facial expression. The facial expression is detected by programming interface with the RPI camera. An alternative method, based on additional emotions which is excluded in our system as disgust and fear. On this emotion included to support the playing of music automatically.

8. CONCLUSION

In this project, we presented a model to recommend a music based on the emotion based detected from the facial expression. This project proposed designed & developed an emotion based music recommendation system using face recognition System. Music are the one that has the power to heal any stress or any kind of emotions. Recent development promises a wide scope in developing emotion based music recommendation system. Thus the proposed system presents Face based emotion recognition system to detect the emotions and play music from the emotion detected. Use either SI (MKS) or CGS as primary units. (SI units are encouraged.) English units may be used as secondary units (in parentheses). An exception would be the use of English units as identifiers in trade, such as “3.5-inch disk drive”. Avoid combining SI and CGS units, such as current in amperes and magnetic field in oersteds. This often leads to confusion because equations do not balance dimensionally. If you must use mixed units, clearly state the units for each quantity that you use in an equation.

9. REFERENCES

[1]. Anagha S.Dhavalikar and Dr. R. K. Kulkarni, “Face Detection and Facial Expression Recognition System” 2014 International Conference on Electronics and Communication System (ICECS -2014)

[2]. Yong-Hwan Lee , Woori Han and Youngseop Kim, “Emotional Recognition from Facial Expression Analysis using Bezier Curve Fitting” 2013 16th International Conference on Network-Based Information Systems.

[3]. Arto Lehtiniemi and Jukka Holm, “Using Animated Mood Pictures in Music Recommendation”, 2012 16th International Conference on Information Visualisation.

[4]. F. Abdat, C. Maaoui and A. Pruski, “Humancomputer interaction using emotion recognition from facial expression”, 2011 UKSim 5th European Symposium on Computer.

[5]. T.-H. Wang and J.-J.J. Lien, “Facial Expression Recognition System Based on Rigid and Non-Rigid Motion Separation and 3D PoseEstimation,” J. Pattern Recognition, vol. 42, no. 5, pp. 962-977, 2009.

[6]Dr. Vrushshen P. Pawar, “Analysis of Facial Expression and Recognition Based On Statistical Approach”, International Journal of Soft Computing and Engineering (IJSCE) Volume-2, May 2012.

[7]Anukriti Dureha “An Accurate Algorithm for Generating a Music Playlist based on Facial Expressions” : IJCA 2014.

[8] Bruce Ferwerda and Markus Schedl “Enhancing Music Recommender Systems with Personality Information and Emotional States”: A Proposal: 2014

[9] Ekman, P. & Friesen, W. V. (1969): The repertoire of nonverbal behavior: Categories, origins, usage, and coding: Semiotica, Vol. 1: 49–98.

[10] Ying-Li Tian, Takeo Kanade, and Jeffrey F. Cohn. (2003): Facial Expression Analysis.

[11] Barbara Raskauskas (2009). Why Do People Listen to Music?

[12] Emily Sohn(2011) Why Music Makes You Happy?

[13] Mary Duenwald (2005). The Physiology of Facial Expressions.

[14] W.K. Teo, Liyanage C De Silva and Prahlad Vadakkepat. (2004): Facial Expression Detection And Recognition System: Journal of The Institution of Engineers, Singapore. Vol 44.

[15] Jagdish Lal Raheja, Umesh Kumar. (2010): Human Facial Expression Detection From Detected In Captured Image Using Back Propagation Neural Network: International Journal of Computer Science & Information Technology (IJCSIT).Vol.2(1).

[16] Zhengyou Zhang. (1998): Feature-Based Facial Expression Recognition: Sensitivity Analysis and Experiments With a Multi-Layer Perceptron: Journal of Pattern Recognition and Artificial Intelligence. Vol. 13(6): 893-911.

[17] Eva Cerezol, Isabelle Hupont, Critina Manresa, Javier Varona, Sandra Baldassarri, Francisco J. Perales, and Francisco J. Seron. (2007): Real-Time Facial Expression Recognition for Natural Interaction: In J. Martí et al. (Eds.): IbPRIA 2007, Part II, LNCS 4478, (pp. 40–47). Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg.

[18] Antoinette L. Bouhuys, Gerda M. Bloem, Ton G.G.Groothuis. (1994): Induction Of Depressed And Elated Mood By Music Influences The Perception Of Facial Emotional Expressions In Healthy Subjects: Journal of Affective